

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258570709>

Development of Portable Experimental Set-up for AFM to Work at Cryogenic Temperature

Article · June 2012

DOI: 10.1063/1.4710113

CITATION

1

READS

1,680

5 authors, including:

D. H. Agarwal

19 PUBLICATIONS 312 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Abrarkhan Pathan

Pandit Deen Dayal Petroleum University

5 PUBLICATIONS 3 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Pina Bhatt

Aditya Silver Oak Institute of Technology

24 PUBLICATIONS 23 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Utpal S Joshi

Gujarat University

88 PUBLICATIONS 525 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

IUAC (UFR-49315) [View project](#)

DAE-BRNS 2011/37P/13/BRNS [View project](#)

A Portable Experimental set-up for AFM to work at cryogenic temperature

D.H. Agrawal, A.M. Pathan, P.M. Bhatt

Cryogenics, Mechanical Engineering Department
L.D. College of Engineering
Ahmedabad, India

dh_agrawal1@yahoo.co.in, abrarkhan87@gmail.com,
er_pina@yahoo.com

B.V. Dave, N.V. Bora

Cryogenics, Mechanical Engineering Department
L.D. College of Engineering
Ahmedabad, India

msbharti@rediffmail.com, nvb_212@yahoo.co.in

Abstract—This paper presents the design aspects of a portable and low cost Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) for very-low temperature investigation of biological, physical and metallurgical samples. The AFM operates at a low temperature i.e. below 100K and in vacuum environment of 10-3mbar. Efficient isolation of all kinds of vibrations up to a natural frequency of 2Hz is achieved to protect the damage of AFM tip. The low temperature is achieved by using LN2 reservoir connected to the base of AFM scan head.

Keywords—Cryogenics, Atomic Force Microscope, Vacuum Chamber, LN2 Reservoir, Vibration Isolation

I. INTRODUCTION

The Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) was invented by Binnig et al. in 1986. In AFM, a tip interacts with the sample surface through a physical phenomenon. Measuring a “local” physical quantity related with the interaction, allows constructing an image of the studied surface. All the data are transferred to a PC, where, with the use of the appropriate software, an image of the surface is created [1].

Fig. 1 shows the Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM, which is a modular, easy to use, and portable instrument. This type of AFM is able to measure small and large samples by dual lens and automatic approach. It is ideal for nanotechnology education and outreach. Its tip can be easily changed without any adjustments and is very affordable [2].

Fig. 1 Atomic Force Microscope.

Fig. 2 shows the principle of Atomic Force Microscope. The AFM measures the forces acting between a fine tip and a sample. The tip is attached to the free end of a cantilever and is brought very close to a surface. Attractive or repulsive forces resulting from interactions between the tip and the surface will cause a positive or negative bending of the cantilever. The bending is detected by means of a laser beam, which is reflected from the backside of the cantilever [3].

Fig. 2 Principle of Atomic Force Microscope.

Explanation of Term – Atomic Force Microscope:
ATOMIC = Ability to view details at atomic and subatomic levels. This increases the understanding of how systems work, leading to new discoveries in many fields.

FORCE = The essential property of AFM is the interaction force between the tip and the sample which depends on their distance.

MICROSCOPE = AFM is incorporated among a broad group of instruments used to image and measure properties of material, chemical, and biological surfaces.

Up to now only a few researchers worldwide have modified the commercially available Atomic Force Microscopes (AFM) to operate at temperatures below 100K, in vacuum and in vibration-free environment. Some of them have developed a permanent set-up that can only be operated in vacuum and low temperatures [4]-[8] while others have designed their own AFM to operate in conventional cryostats [9]-[11]. However, a portable AFM that combines very low temperatures, operation in vacuum and with vibration isolation along with robustness, flexibility and ease-of-handling is still lacking. The setup that is described in the present article fulfils these requirements. It is very small; matching with the most commercial low-temperature facilities requires to elaborate vibration damping and uses very modest amount of vacuum. The special physical project, for which purpose the set-up is designed, is to enable the AFM to work at cryogenic temperature. The aim is to achieve quantitative variation between experiments carried out in ambient and cryogenic condition.

The experimental set-up is an assembly of three synchronized parts viz. Liquid Nitrogen Reservoir (LN₂ Reservoir), Vacuum Chamber (VC) and Vibration Isolation Table (VI-table).

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. LN₂ Reservoir

The LN₂ Reservoir is developed to provide the low temperature for cooling the thin film specimen below 100K. Fig. 3 shows the 2D view of LN₂ reservoir. The reservoir is a double walled vessel made up of SS304. The space between inner and outer vessel is evacuated to prevent the heat leak from atmosphere to Liquid Nitrogen. The use of vacuum insulation essentially eliminates two components of heat transfer-solid conduction and gaseous convection. Heat is transferred across the annular space of a vacuum-insulated vessel by radiation from the hot outer jacket to the cold inner liquid within the annular space, which however, is quite small. SS304 is used for fabrication as it has excellent properties at cryogenic temperature such as low heat transfer rate, high strength, better corrosion resistance, fracture toughness, fabricability, etc.

Fig. 3 Two- dimensional view of LN₂ Reservoir.

Fig. 4 Model of LN₂ Reservoir.

The Reservoir is attached to the base of Vacuum Chamber. A flange is extended from the inner vessel that is bolted to the base plate to fix the vessel. Liquid Nitrogen is introduced into the vessel via a fill-line provided at the top and excess LN₂ is drained out through a drain line from the bottom. These fill and drain line are also double walled with vacuum in between the two walls. An ultrapure copper rod due to its high thermal conductivity ($k = 385\text{W/mK}$) and heat transfer co-efficient is used as *cold finger*. The cold finger is dipped in LN₂ and extended to the base of AFM to cool the sample stage. The copper rod not only serves to transmit cooling effect but also prevents the vibrations that are generated due to LN₂ boiling from affecting the tip of AFM. It is passed through a PTFE (Teflon) sleeve to prevent lateral heat conduction.

B. Vacuum Chamber

When an AFM is designed to work at cryogenic temperatures there arises a problem of condensation of moisture over the surface of the sample as well as on the tip of the cantilever. However, if both, the AFM and the sample are placed in an evacuated chamber than this problem can be eliminated. The Vacuum Chamber is thus developed to house the AFM scan head along with sample to isolate them from atmospheric condition. Fig. 5 gives detailed view of Vacuum chamber. The chamber is made up of Aluminium due to its special merits over other materials. Aluminium has inherently less Hydrogen & Carbon than stainless steel and consequently less H₂, H₂O, & hydrocarbon vapour at high vacuum and ultra high vacuum levels. Aluminium vacuum chambers with a thin dense aluminium oxide serves as a resistive barrier reducing diffusion and desorption of high vacuum contaminates (Hydrogen, Oxygen & Carbon). Once baked, aluminium vacuum chambers generally cycle to high vacuum levels faster than stainless chambers and require less pumping. In addition to aluminium's excellent vacuum properties it is also a more versatile material from a manufacturing standpoint.

Fig. 5 Two-dimensional view of Vacuum Chamber.

Fig. 6 Fabricated Vacuum Chambers.

The vacuum chamber must be sufficiently big to accommodate the instrument with the connectors and cables that synchronize the instrument with the computer and should provide a base for mounting the sample below the tip of AFM scan head. At the same time, the chamber must not be too big that much time is elapsed in achieving the desired pressure in the chamber. The AFM scan head is 40 to 50 mm high, so the height of the chamber is taken as 100 mm. Though the length and width of the scan head is 65mm, but the cables connected at the rear side of the scan head makes the effective length of the scan head 150mm. Taking this into consideration, the vacuum chamber is made of 200mm diameter. The instrument is kept offset from the centre and the effective size of the vacuum chamber is reduced.

The vacuum chamber is mounted on a base plate that serves as a platform for the AFM. The scan head is precisely aligned on the base plate because small misalignments, even in microns, drastically affect the images generated by the scan head and the tip may crash on to the sample surface.

The designed internal pressure is 0.001mbar that is created by using a mechanical rotary pump having a pumping speed of 60lit/min. The pump is connected to the chamber through bellows so that the vibrations of the pump do not transmit to the chamber. A thermal conductivity gauge (Pirani Gauge) is used to measure the pressure inside the chamber. Two view ports are provided for *in situ* visibility of the experiment as well as to identify the position of sample with respect to the tip of the AFM. Vacuum feed-throughs in the form of BNC jacks are used to input the wires of the temperature sensor and specially designed feed-throughs are employed to input the cable of Atomic Force Microscope.

C. Vibration Isolation Table

Fig. 7 Two-dimensional view of Vibration Isolation Table.

Operation at low temperatures brings the benefits of low thermal drift and low thermal noise, which are required for high-resolution measurements with AFM. On the other hand, very low temperature refrigeration techniques often hamper the efforts to achieve high-resolution measurements due to the introduction of mechanical vibrations. Furthermore, the physical space available, especially when a vacuum is required, is often too limited to allow an effective cryogenic vibration-isolation stage. The efforts to address these challenges are concentrated in the following two elements: A cooling system that has very low intrinsic vibration noise, and a good external vibration-isolation system to reduce transmission of vibrations from the external environment to the AFM stage.

The VI table is used to prevent the external vibration from reaching the tip of AFM. Fig.7 shows 2D view of VI table. The table is made up of Mild steel with vibration dampers at the bottom. Mild steel has very high strength to weight ratio, yield strength, hardness, toughness, able to resist shocks and impact loading, good weldability and machinability. The dampers are made up of hardened rubber that has a very high stiffness ($k = 3000\text{N/m}$) and the weight of the table is quite high so as to absorb all the amplitudes without transferring them to the set-up. The set-up is mounted on the VI table and held rigid by legs at the four corners of the base plate. The table also serves as a medium to house the LN_2 reservoir. As the natural frequency of the AFM is 2kHz, and a VI table with rubber having a natural frequency 2Hz is used for vibration isolation, the overall transfer function for intermediate frequencies is a constant, 10^{-6} or 120db. Therefore, the rigidity of the AFM unit is the achieved, which is the most important factor in vibration isolation.

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULT

LN_2 has emerged as the best solution to get the temperature in the range of mid 80K. As the reservoir is located just below the tip of AFM, losses during heat conduction are minimized. The PTFE sleeve serves as a good insulator in preventing lateral heat conduction and maximum cooling is achieved.

Fig. 8 Two-dimensional view of Assembly

Fig. 9 Assembled Experimental setup

Vacuum insulation prevents heat transfer by conduction and convection. The precise alignment of AFM within the Vacuum Chamber eliminates the danger to the tip during mishandling. Reduction of pressure to 0.001mbar reduces the condensation of moisture on the tip. It also prevents the accumulation of dust particle causing contamination of sample resulting into distortion of image obtained by AFM. The VI table has considerably reduced the vibration up to a vibration frequency of 2Hz. It helps in obtaining better performance of the AFM.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Atomic force microscope for molecular level imaging of small structures, both natural and artificial to operate at cryogenic temperature has been designed. Various critical parameters such as designing of vacuum chamber to reduce pressure up to 10^{-3} mbar, cold finger and LN_2 reservoir as well as vibration free environment have been carefully considered. The system is capable of imaging the nano-structures, in both contact and non-contact modes of operations. In-house designing of vacuum feedthroughs, copper cold-finger etc. has substantially reduced the cost of the equipment, which is otherwise, extremely expensive commercially.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank Department of Science and Technology, Government of India for providing the fund under the DST-FIST (Level-I) support to procure the AFM set up.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Debuschewitz, F. M'unstermann, V. Kunej, and E. Scheer, "A Compact and Versatile Scanning Tunnelling Microscope with High Energy Resolution for Use in a 3He Cryostat": *Journal of Low Temperature Physics*, Vol. 147, Nos. 3/4, May 2007.
- [2] The nanoscience website Available: <http://www.nanoscience.com/>
- [3] Arantxa Vilalta-Clemente and Kathrin Gloystein "Principles of Atomic Principles Force Microscopy(AFM)" *Physics of Advanced Materials Winter School*, 2008.
- [4] M.Kugler, Ch. Renner, Ø. Fischer, V. Mikheev, and G. Batey, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* Vol.71, 1475,2000.
- [5] T.Matsui, H. Kambara, and H. Fukuyama, *J. Low. Temp. Phys.* 121 803 (2000).
- [6] T.Matsui, H. Kambara, I. Ueda, T. Shishido, Y. Miyatake, and H. Fukuyama, *Physica B* 329, 1653 2003.
- [7] A.J. Heinrich, C. P. Lutz, J. A. Gupta, and D. M. Eigler, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 696, 2000.
- [8] J.Wiebe, A. Wachowiak, F. Meier, D. Haude, T. Foster, M. Morgenstern, and R. Wiesendanger *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, Vol.75, 4871,2004.
- [9] P. Davidsson, H. Olin, M. Persson, and S. Pehrson, *Ultramicroscopy*,42–44, 1470,1992.
- [10] S.H.Pan E. W. Hudson, and J. C. Davis," 3He -Refrigerator based very low temperature scanning tunnelling microscope". *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* Vol. 70, pp.1459-1463,1999.
- [11] N.Moussy H. Courtois, and B. Pannetier, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 72, 128,2001.